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Occupational Safety, Health Hazards and Productivity of Plantation Workers in Tea Sector of Sri Lanka: A Case Study at St. Coombs Estate, Talawakelle

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ABSTRACT

Sri Lanka's plantation industry is the country's single biggest employer providing direct livelihoods to nearly 200,000 people. Occupational health hazards (OHH) refer to the potential risks to the health and safety of workers in their workplaces. Generally, workers maximize their earnings by exposing themselves to extreme work conditions *viz.* long working hours and improper rest breaks, for economic reasons and ultimately affect their health. Tea plantation workers are exposed to several hazards in their workplaces due to physical, biological, mechanical, chemical and psychosocial factors. Therefore, the present study was conducted to investigate the relationship between labor productivity of tea estate workers and their potential occupational and health safety, while examining various OHH and the degree of vulnerability. Further, this study was conducted to explore the health problems associated with OHH and to suggest measures to mitigate the possible impacts of OHH. A survey was conducted to collect data using a pretested semi-structured questionnaire. Altogether, 100 workers were randomly selected from the two divisions of estate. Descriptive statistics, categorical data analysis and regression analysis were performed for the statistical analysis. The results revealed that 5.4% and 18.8% of the workers were exposed to chemical and mechanical hazards, respectively. Considering the other three hazards, (Biological, Physical and Psychosocial) at least 23.4%, 14.6%, 38.4% of workers were infected. Study suggest that the workers should be responsible to follow the safety measures namely properly wearing of personal protective equipment, spraying of chemicals with appropriate protective gears to mitigate the hazard infections.

KEYWORDS: Health hazards, Occupational health safety, Tea plantation, Vulnerability

INTRODUCTION

Sri Lanka is one of the largest tea-producing countries globally and is home to many tea plantation workers. For more than century, Sri Lanka's tea industry has been the backbone of the island's economy contributing 40% of export revenue, 30% to the agricultural labor force and also Gross Domestic Production (Bandara, 1996; Kumar and Vellaichamy, 2020).

The process of tea cultivation is laborious and time consuming, requiring cautious care. Tea plantation workers in Sri Lanka put hours of hard work into the job. Organizations are committed to fighting for the rights and protection of tea plantation workers in countries like Sri Lanka.

Among the plantation economies, Sri Lanka has the third largest estate work force, next only to India and Brazil. Recent research studies place more than 10% of the active work force in the country being absorbed in the tea industry (Jegathesan, 2018).

Therefore, the tea industry is the most labor intensive among the other plantation industries, giving direct employment to about

700,000 workers on 194,000 hectares of land. In addition, at least another 200,000 are in indirect, tea-related employment (Bandara, 1996; Kutty and Priyadarshan, 2018). Because of these characteristics, there is no doubt that the labor is the most important factor, which affect to the productivity of a tea plantation. Therefore, the productivity of labor is highly correlated with the total productivity of tea estate. However, labor productivity recorded in tea plantations is low when compared with competitive labor markets both domestic and foreign.

It's a known fact that, the agriculture sector employments are mostly hazardous occupations carried out in difficult and sometimes dangerous working conditions. The specific hazards facing plantation workers vary from one estate to another. Tea being the most labor-intensive of all the plantation crops grown in Sri Lanka, about 60 % of the cost of production is incurred on labour on average. Workload at the plantations are basically manual in nature. The tea factory, which processes the green tea leaves, is mechanized, however it employs less than 10 % of the total

labour force. Field workers are engaged in plucking (harvesting) and activities related to the maintenance of the estates and its tea bushes.

These include hoeing, weeding, pruning of the bushes, and drainage. Female workers are mainly engaged in plucking of tea leaves and in light maintenance work. The males to pluck tea leaves, however in addition they are engaged in strenuous agronomic activities. Adolescents more or less do the same work as the adults, and are also engaged in spraying of pesticides, which can be harmful to their health (Forastieri, 2001; Mittal and Gupta, 2008). Therefore, present study was carried out to investigate the association between labour productivity of tea estate workers and their potential occupational and health safety, while examining the various occupational health hazards, the degree of vulnerability and resulting health problems and suggest measures for mitigating the possible occupational health hazards.

METHODOLOGY

Location

The study was carried out in Tea Research Institute, Talawakele, Sri Lanka from November 2021 to March 2022.

Data Collection

A survey was conducted using a pretested semi structured questionnaire to gather primary data of workers. Participant were selected randomly from two divisions of St. Coombs' estate, Thalawakelle. Data were collected from 100 workers (pluckers and sundry workers) through face-to-face interviews.

Measures

The questionnaire consisted of ten parts namely, general information, demographic characteristics, activity profile, worker productivity, health condition of the respondents, health security, economic security, habitat security, social security and causes of vulnerability to occupational health hazard. General information consist of basic details *viz.* name and employee number and other demographic characteristics were collected. Worker productivity were quantified from the information collected related to the green leaf kilo grams plucked per day, weeding, pruning, and fertilizer application per day basis. Health conditions of the respondents associated with chemically hazard, mechanical hazard, psychosocial hazard, biological hazard and physical hazard were collected.

Health security of the workers is associated with the availability of health facilities and food security. Economic security is associated with the income and expenditure.

Habitat security is associated with the water facilities and domestic safety measures. Social security is associated with the medical care, housing and loan. Causes of vulnerability to occupational health hazard need to have consisted with low income, lack of savings, sanitary facilities, protective tools etc.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the demographic information and occupational health hazards related data collected from face-to-face interviews with the workers. Responses were collected from workers with respect to mitigating the possible occupational health hazard to tea estate workers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics of the Sample

As described in Table 1, there were 100 respondents in the sample and 82% of them were females whereas the 18% of them were males. All of them were Tamils and no any Buddhist or Islam ethnicity was recorded. And 97% of the respondents were belong to Hindu religion, 1% of the respondents were belong to Muslim religion and 2% of the respondents was burgher. Furthermore, 38% of the people have completed their O/Ls, 8% of the people were not attempt to school, 35% of the people have passed grade five exam and 19% of the people have completed grade eight. Also 99% of them were married, while 1% of them was single. According to the job status, 88% of the sample were registered for their job and 12% of them were engaged as casual job. Among the sample collected, 82% of farmers are pluckers and 18% of them are pruners.

Occupational Health Hazards and Safety Measurements

Almost all of respondents mentioned that they were suffered several health hazards. As described in figure 1, the present study revealed that 5.04% of the workers were exposed to the chemical hazards whereas, 18.77% and 38.27% of the people were exposed to the mechanical hazards and psychosocial hazards respectively. Among the results, 14.56% of the people were exposed to the biological hazards, when considering the physical hazard, 33.35% of the people were exposed to the physical hazards.

Health Condition and Activity Profile

Table 2 clearly described the chemical hazards affected by the workers. Majority of the workers were affected by the 0.2 severity level which responsible for the poisoned hazards, 0.78 severity level were affected by skin infection and only 0.03 severity level were affected by the burned. Furthermore,

considering about the mechanical hazards affected by the workers, majority of the workers were affected by the 0.18 which responsible for the cut to pre-edge whereas, 0.17 severity level were affected by injuries during uprooting, cleaning, pruning. Moreover, 0.26, 0.25 and 0.14 of severity levels were affected by slippery falls, injuries in shoulder arms during lifting and respiratory problems due to chemical spraying, fertilizer application respectively. Furthermore, considering about the psychosocial hazard affected by the workers, majority of the workers are affected by the 0.26 severity level which responsible for the work related stress due to work load. Among the results, 0.22, 0.1, 0.19, 0.24, 0.23 and 0.24 of severity levels were affected by pressure to meet targets, job insecurity, bullying among tea workers, and lack of welfare condition, no promotion and no job satisfaction respectively.

As presented in Table 3, workers were frequently affected by various disease conditions and majority of the workers were affected by abdominal pain and 42% workers fully recovered, 10% workers partially recovering quickly, 3% recorded as not recovering quickly and 45% recorded with not having permanent symptom, affected by headache number of respondents 32% fully recovered headache, 14% headache partially, permanent symptoms. affected by hypertension number of respondents 0% not hypertension, 1% partially hypertension, 18% not recovering hypertension, 81% not permanent symptom hypertension, affected by sleep problem number of respondents 11% fully recovered sleep problem, 6% partially sleep problem, 1% not recovering sleep problem, 82% not permanent symptom sleep problem affected by musculoskeletal pain number of respondents 24% fully recovered musculoskeletal pain, 14% partially musculoskeletal pain, 13% not recovering musculoskeletal pain, 49% not

permanent symptom, affected by depression number of respondent 100% not depression.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characters of the sample

Parameter	Category	Percentage
Gender	Female	82%
	Male	18%
Ethnicity	Hindu	100%
	Buddhist	0.0%
	Islam	0.0%
	Sinhala	0.0%
	Other	0.0%
Religion	Tamil	97%
	Muslim	1%
	Burgher	2%
Education	No Schooling	8%
	Grade 5 Passé	35%
	Grade 8 Passé	19%
	O/ Completed	38%
Marital	Never Married	1%
	Married	99%
	Divorced	0.0%
Job	Registered	88%
	Casual	12%
Nature	Pluckers	82%
	Sundry Workers	18%

Table 2. Severity levels of health hazards

Chemical hazard	Severity level	Mechanical hazard	Severity level	Psychosocial hazard	Severity level
Poisoned	0.2	Cut to pre-edges	0.18	Work-related stress due to work load	0.26
Skin infection	0.78	Injuries during uprooting, cleaning, pruning	0.17	Pressure to meet targets	0.22
Burned	0.03	Slippery falls	0.26	Job insecurity	0.1
		Injuries in shoulder arms during lifting	0.25	Bulling among tea workers	0.19
		Respiratory problems due to chemical spraying, fertilizer application	0.14	Lack of welfare condition	0.24
				No promotion	0.23
				No job satisfaction	0.24

Table 3. Health problem exposed by the tea plantation workers

Diseases	Fully recovered	Partially	Not recovering	Permanent symptom
Abdominal Pain	42	10	3	45
Headache	32	14	15	39
Hypertension	0	1	18	81
Sleep Problem	11	6	1	82
Musculoskeletal Pain	24	14	13	49
Depression	0	0	0	0

Social Benefit and Safety Wears

The Table 4 depicts that the social security affected the workers majority of the workers were affected by 79% were affected by the medical care, 13% are affected by the housing, 17% are affected by the food for children, 15% are affected by the daycare, 44% are affected by the long, 63% are affected by the protective wear, 57% are affected by the masks, 33% were affected by the gloves, 1% were affected by the boots, 2% were affected by the hats, finally 20% were affected by the sanitizers.

Table 4. Social security

Social security variable	Percentage (%)
Medical Care	79
Housing	13
Food For Children	17
Daycare	15
Long	44
Protective Wears	63
Masks	57
Gloves	33
Boots	1
Hats	2
Sanitizers	20

Causes of Vulnerability of Occupational Health Hazards

The Table 5 describes the Causes of vulnerability of occupational health hazards. Among the results, considering about the lack of nutritional diet, 28.71%, 69.14% and 2.123% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability and highly vulnerability respectively. Whereas, related to the low income, 51%, 23% and 26% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability and highly vulnerability respectively. Considering the harsh environment, 39.34%, 55.06% and 5.62% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability and highly vulnerability respectively.

Moreover, considering about the lack of healthy housing facilities, 43.01%, 52.69% and 4.3% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability highly vulnerability respectively. Whereas, Lack of sanitary facilities performed that 47.94%, 50% and 2.04% of low vulnerability, medium vulnerability and highly vulnerability respectively. Focusing on Lack of protective clothing/tools, 42.55%, 51.06% and 6.38% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability and highly vulnerability respectively. Whereas, considering about the

low, medium and high vulnerability levels, Lack of protective tools performed that 41.67%, 53.57% and 4.76% respectively. Considering about the Lack of saving, 45%, 50% and 5% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability and highly vulnerability respectively. Moreover, considering the no opportunity to additional family income sources, 48.33%, 41.67% and 10% state that there were low vulnerability, medium vulnerability highly vulnerability, respectively.

Table 5. Causes of the vulnerability of occupational safety, health hazards

Causes	Low	Medium	High
Lack of nutritional diet	28.72	69.14	2.123
Low income	51	23	26
Harsh environment	39.34	55.06	5.62
Lack of healthy housing facilities	43.01	52.69	4.3
Lack of sanitary facilities	47.94	50	2.04
Lack of protective clothing/tools	42.55	51.06	6.38
Lack of protective tools	41.67	53.57	4.76
Lack of saving	45	50	5
No opportunity to additional family income sources	48.33	41.67	10

CONCLUSIONS

The study attempted to find out the occupational health hazards of tea plantation workers in Sri Lanka. Among the results, 5.0% and 18.8%, of the workers, were not exposed to chemical and mechanical hazards, respectively. Considering the other three hazards, (Biological, Physical and Psychosocial) at least 14. %, 23.3%, 38.2% of workers were infected. Moreover, to mitigate the hazard infections, the workers should be responsible to follow the safety measures, for instance properly wearing personal protective equipment, etc.

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